

A common methodology for fuel price comparison at a common unit aligned with EU consumers perception

Aristomenis SKYLLAKOS ¹, Antonis PEPPAS ^{2*}, Ilias PASIOS ¹, Chrysa POLITI ², Sotirios KOTTARIDIS ², Lampros KARALIS ²

¹ Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, Directorate of Technical Control and Vehicle Service Facilities, Athens, Greece, email AS a.skillakos@yme.gov.gr, IP h.pasios@yme.gov.gr

² School of Mining and Metallurgical Engineering, Laboratory of Metallurgy, National Technical University of Athens, Athens, Greece, email: AP peppas@metal.ntua.gr, CP chrysapol@metal.ntua.gr, SK skottaridis@metal.ntua.gr, LK lkaralis@metal.ntua.gr

* Corresponding author: AP, peppas@metal.ntua.gr, Assistant Professor, tel. +30 210 772 2219, 157 80 Zografos, Athens, Greece

Abstract

The connection between transport and its environmental impact is especially critical in the progress towards sustainable development. The energy demand in the transport section increased by 7% overall throughout the five years to 2020 as reported by EUROSTAT [1]. The numbers of transport services and traffic volume grew respectively [2] with the European fleet to be expanded by around three million cars and trucks annually. In this line, transport sector led to environmental issues as it accounts for the 24% of global carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions (if we only consider CO₂ emissions from energy) [3]. European Union (EU) is committed to achieve GHG emissions reduction to 80–95% below 1990-levels by 2050 and thus initiatives and policy frameworks increase the penetration of eco-friendly vehicles in the market. In this frame, the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Directive 2014/94/EU [4] (hereinafter referred to as "AFID") introduces a consumer-oriented framework towards alternative fuels. Following AFID directions, a Programme Support Action (PSA) called "Assisting Member States in the implementation of a common methodology for AFs unit price comparison in accordance with Directive 2014/94/EU - FPC4Consumers" was implemented for delivering a common methodology for comparing fuel prices in euros/100km, aligned with EU consumers' perception. These implementing acts aimed to increase consumer awareness and provide fuel price transparency in a consistent way across the Union, and the display of fuels information should not confuse the consumers. For this purpose, an online questionnaire and pilot actions within EU countries were performed, with almost 8000 consumers preferences evaluated in relation to display format, content and location displayed at filling stations. The evaluation of the responses contributed to the optimisation of Fuel Price Comparison (FPC) displays and the development of the common methodology proposed which was adapted from most of EU countries and applied at the end of 2020.

Keywords: alternative fuels; fuel price comparison; transportation policy, vehicles use, consumers perception

Nomenclature

AF	Alternative fuel	FPC	Fuel price comparison
AFID	Alternative Fuel Infrastructure Directive	FCV	Fuel cell vehicle
AFV	Alternative fuel vehicle	h.b.	Highly blended
CF	Conventional fuel	LPG	Liquid petroleum gas
GHG	Greenhouse Gas	MS	Member State
CNG	Compressed natural gas	PEV	Pure electric vehicle
EC	European Commission	PSA	Programme Support Action
EU	European Union	SUV	Sport utility vehicle

1. Introduction

1.1. Consumer-oriented AF transition actions

The road transport is proved a detrimental activity for the environment, as it consumes over 80% of the total final energy used in the transport sector and contributes over 75% to its total CO₂ emissions. EU is committed to achieve Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions reduction to 80–95% below 1990-levels by 2050 and thus initiatives and support actions increase the penetration of eco-friendly vehicles in the market.

According to literature [5, 6, 7], it is shown that vehicle purchase intention and willingness-to-buy by consumers are affected by several parameters including the vehicles, the fuel prices and purchase costs, the charging and refuelling infrastructure, the fuel taxation, the vehicles' performance, the possible government grants for alternative fuel vehicles (AFVs), the environmental concern and awareness, the public acceptance and understanding of global air pollution. However, the significance of each parameter differs among different countries.[6] Most of these barriers are linked to technical and economic factors and can raise barriers in the adoption of AFVs while in few cases the barriers can be overcome by the current technologies. Such cases refer to the public knowledge, perception, and acceptance of AFs. Nevertheless, increase in adopting AFVs could be achieved by focusing on the consumers' perception barriers through addressing the car salespeople's and consumer's knowledge on AFVs and the environmental issues, as well as their encouragement by governments and policymakers to accept and use AFVs.

According to a consumer survey carried out by the German Energy Agency (DENA) [7] among representative national panels of 3000 respondents in France, Germany and Italy, a key parameter of comparing the different fuel is their price. In specific, the most effective and understandable way to compare fuel prices is to express them in euros or national currency per 100km. This concept served as a basis for further investigation on the consumers' preferences in relation to the format, content, and location of the fuel prices comparison under the same unit. However, despite the numerous consumers' preferences surveys towards AFVs performed in several countries, an aggregated consumers' point of view in EU level could further contribute to increasing the use of AFs.

On those grounds, the AFID introduces a consumer-oriented framework towards alternative fuels (AFs), which aims to stimulate the dissemination of AFs to the consumers and increase their environmental awareness. In addition, the AFID intends to spur the use of AFVs in Europe, to reduce emissions and thus lead to a low-carbon society. The scope of the AFID is summarised in recital 51, which explicitly states, "Simple and easy-to-compare information on the prices of different fuels could play a significant role in enabling vehicle users to better evaluate the relative cost of individual fuels available on the market. Therefore, when fuel prices are displayed at a fuel station, in particular for natural gas and hydrogen, it should be possible for unit price comparison to conventional fuels (CFs), such as '1 petrol litre equivalent', to be displayed for information purposes." To this regard, Art. 7 para. 3 of the Directive states: "Where appropriate, and in particular for natural gas and hydrogen, when fuel prices are displayed at a fuel station, a comparison between the relevant unit prices shall be displayed for information purposes. The display of this information shall not mislead or confuse the user."

1.2. Framework of "FPC4Consumers"

The Commission has decided to award a grant for the action entitled "Assisting MS in the implementation of a common methodology for AFs unit price comparison following Directive 2014/94/EU" ("FPC4Consumers") starting on 01/02/2019 with duration: 20 months. The FPC4Consumers consortium consisted of Greece (the coordinator), Cyprus, Germany, Finland, France, Croatia, Netherlands, Portugal, and Spain. The objective of this PSA was to assist MS with the implementation of Art. 7.3 of the AFID. In specific, MS shall provide information on fuel prices to enable consumers to compare the fuel/running costs of vehicles with different fuels in a common unit (€/100km). In this regard, the Commission Implementing Regulation on FPC defined a methodology for calculating the FPC values related to the Art. 7.3 of the AFID. The aims of the PSA were to support the consistent implementation of the provisions of Art. 7.3 of the AFID, and define the format, content, and location of the information to be displayed at the filling stations. In addition, pilot actions were foreseen to assess consumer perspective concerning FPC displays at the filling stations and to provide recommendations/guidelines for a harmonized implementation of Art. 7.3 of the AFID. The overall objective

was to support MS in making information available to the consumers at the filling/charging stations through digital tools to ensure consumers/users can make a straightforward comparison between the fuel costs of vehicles with different fuel types as well as disseminate the common methodology for FPC calculations and raise awareness of AF suppliers, media, and consumers.

1.3. Online survey in FPC4Consumers

In the framework of FPC4Consumers, the elaboration, and implementation of an online consumer questionnaire was performed aiming to define the contents, format, and location of the information on fuel prices to be compared and displayed at filling/charging stations including validation of the defined options with consumers/drivers. The conducted statistical analysis of the questionnaire responses, the different trade-offs consumers, who are willing to have under their possession, buy a vehicle depending on its fuel type and was examined the impact of lifestyle and preferences for powertrains, technology (inside and outside of the vehicle) on consumers' choices were determined. The study also seeks to assess the customer experience and the factors influenced by the pricing methods followed. The evaluation of the results exported from the online questionnaire is focused on understanding the influential factors concerning consumers' mobility decisions as new transportation models (e.g., car sharing, etc.) emerge. In total, 7612 respondents participated in the online survey, covering different ages, dwelling environments and vehicles' preferences and needs. In this manner, consumer opinions were considered in the development and finalization of the FPC displays. The analysis of online surveys that were carried out among European consumers combined with the related stakeholders' reactions acquired during dissemination actions aimed to address: (1) the types of information consumers are looking at, when purchasing and fuelling their vehicle; (2) the level of awareness regarding AFs; and (3) the understanding and effectiveness of AFs price comparison.

The aim of this study is to present the in-depth analysis and evaluation of the online questionnaire results. All actions performed, target on understanding both consumers' and stakeholders' perspectives on FPC. This holistic approach allows the evaluation of FPC in terms of effectiveness and feasibility. Therefore, the outcome of the analysis resulted in the identification of recommendations on the most effective ways to communicate to the European consumers the FPC at the fuel station and through an online tool in a transparent and complete manner. The survey results presented in this study were further analysed in the PSA public deliverable D6.3 "Final Report" as well as presented on an Online Workshop organised on September 2020.

2. Survey design, methods, and implementation

2.1. Purpose of the study

The survey was performed to evaluate the impact of this information to consumers' perspective in correspondence with AFs. The objective of this study is the understanding of the different trends and approaches about vehicle purchasing, and consequently the assessment of the awareness, or lack of it, concerning AFs. Many studies have shown the inconsistent combination of an increased eco-friendly tendency of the general population and an inexplicably low rate of AFVs in the streets. This fact can only be perceived as a difficulty communicating the benefits concerning the AFV market to the consumers. Therefore, this survey was carried out to gather information concerning the areas of vehicle purchasing criteria, environmental awareness and AFV awareness, as well as the communication and display methods of FPC.

2.2. Survey design

The survey comprised of all the core elements of questionnaire evaluation, such as the organisation of the questions and items of interest, the assessment of the survey quality, resources handling and eventually the overall satisfaction for both questioners and respondents. [8] Key components such as the sample selection and construction were individually examined as suggested by the respective bibliography. [8, 9] Among different options, an online survey method was selected, due to the advantages of the digital approach. [10]

A basic point scale and closed-ended question combination model was selected for the assessment of the different topics in the study. More specifically, the topics in this survey are divided in six groups; demographic,

socio-economic, vehicle usage, fuel usage, vehicle purchasing, and environmental awareness. Demographic information was collected for the establishment of the survey sample, such as personal information (e.g., age), knowledge of the AFs, segments of vehicles running with CFs or AFs, and environmental awareness. Questions were also accompanied by additional explanatory information for the facilitation of the user-friendly approach. A “Comments and questions” section was implemented at the end of the questionnaire to enable constructive feedback and a more interactive experience for the participants. As a result, a 22-questions survey was designed, with an estimated completion time of 4 minutes. Additionally, a question concerning the car usage frequency was used as a filter for ensuring that respondents will be familiar with questionnaire context, leading to more reliable results, as the sample will be representative and relevant to the targets of the online questionnaire. In case a participant answered that he had never used a car, his questionnaire would stop and be finalised, thus preventing the “contamination” of the statistics from participants not relevant to this study, while preserving their own time as well.

2.3. Data collection and sample

The survey was distributed to nine MS, in accordance with their respective population, through a dedicated website. With the intention of ensuring sizable and adequate samples, MS collected and analysed responses from minimum 1500 consumers in each of the participating MS whose population is more than 20 million inhabitants and 700 consumers for MS with population less than 20 million. It is mentioned that coverage of consumers from different regions/cities was targeted. The questionnaire was communicated to the consumers through a user-friendly interface and a simple structure so to ensure maximum engagement. Simultaneously, both anonymization of the respondents and ethical issues were taken into consideration to ensure data security and personal data protection through the entire process. The questionnaire was complied with the relevant EU standards and regulations, with respect to personal data protection [11, 12] and ethical issues and every response was voluntary and anonymous.

2.4. Implementation of online survey

The online consumer questionnaire was translated into national languages and was uploaded to the FPC4Consumers website. The option of participants taking the survey in their own native language was implemented in line with the PSA framework requirements. In some MS, the questionnaire was hosted on the official website of the participated Ministry. The questionnaire was created using the “google forms” platform and was launched for a two-month period from July of 2019 until September of 2019. The link of the questionnaire was posted on the website of the project and it was promoted through social media. Special focus was given on promotion through twitter, where consecutive rounds of sponsored promotion were carried out. Through the aforementioned process, the message concerning the project and the survey that was carried out was seen by more than 352000 twitter users.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Results of the online survey

3.1.1. Demographic analysis

The first section of the questionnaire concerned demographic information, namely gender, age, urbanisation level for the identification of the exact place of occupancy for the different MS and vehicle usage frequency. The parameters of age, Degree of Urbanization, as derived from the zip code and the new degree of urbanization (DEGURBA) [13] classification data, size of owned vehicle and corresponding categories (based on the European Commission (EC) segmentation [14]) and average daily distance covered by the participants, were grouped in three groups respectively, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Evaluation of respondents based on the following parameters

Age	Degree of urbanisation	Vehicle size	Daily distance
Young Adults (19-35)	Urban	Small vehicle	Short distance (<20km)
Middle-aged Adults (36-55)	Suburban	Medium vehicle	Medium distance(20-50km)
Older Adults (>56)	Rural	Large vehicle	(Very)Long distance (>50km)

The questions of the survey were analysed based on the abovementioned parameters in order to guarantee the effective evaluation of the consumers FPC preferences and the determination of the FPC impact on the specific consumer groups. The results present a slightly equal distribution of the respondents in these categories. In case a respondent did not provide a valid answer (i.e., not valid zip code), the response was excluded from the related category.

Figure 1. Demographic results (1) Gender, (2) Age, (3) Urbanisation level

With a respectable overall response rate, a sample of 7612 was collected. The collected sample consisted of 60.4% males, 39.4% females, and 0.2% other, which is considered indicative of the vehicle owning general population (also see Figure 1. In terms of the participants' age, a 64% were ages between 18 and 55, followed by and 28% ages between 55 and 78, considered also indicative for the vehicle using general population. Additionally, a 90% of the participants declared using their vehicle several times a week, validating the sample as representative of the aimed target group. A 94% were found to use Petrol/ Diesel running vehicles, proving the need of AF awareness communication even more critical.

The next item of concern was the average distance usually covered daily by the participants. The options were grouped into four categories, those being the short distance (<20 km), intermediate distance (<50 km), long distance (<150 km) and the very long distance (>150 km). The results of this question can be seen in Figure 2. At an overall level, short distances and intermediate distances consisted the majority's daily driving demand, with a similar distribution of 38.8% and 41.6 % respectively, while 16.6% of the participants covered long distances daily and a 2.9% covering more than 150 km.

Figure 2. What average distance do you usually cover by car, daily?

3.1.2. Vehicle and driving routine

The vehicle and driving questions group concerned the information regarding the vehicles the participants owned, as well as information about their own personal driving routine, as a kind of a secondary demographic analysis about the driving status. The participants were asked about the type of vehicle they drive in relation to the EC classification, as shown in Table 2. The results show that among EU, 12.8% of drivers usually drives mini/small cars, 29.4% drives compact cars, 31.4% middle/intermediate cars, 11.5% drives large cars, 10.5% drives Sport utility vehicles (SUVs), 2.4% drives vans while a 2% of the participants declared driving other kind of vehicles.

Table 2. Passenger car classification defined by the EC

REGULATION (EEC) No 4064/89 Segments		Online Questionnaire
A	City cars	mini
B	Small cars	small
C	Medium cars	compact
D	Large cars	middle / intermediate
E	Executive cars	large
F	Luxury cars	large
S	Sport coupes	other
J	Sport utility cars, also known as Sport Utility Vehicles (SUV)	SUV
M	Multi-purpose cars, also known as Multi-Purpose Vehicles (MPV)	van

The following question asked for the type of fuel/energy the participants use in their vehicles. The results showed that CFs (petrol/diesel) are by far the most popular choice within MS. Specifically, over 90% stated driving vehicles burning CFs. Most participants using AFs opted for the use of Liquid petroleum gas (LPG) (2.7%) It is noteworthy, that only a miniscule 0.04% opted for the high promising Hydrogen alternative. The pattern of fuel choice in EU level is identical with the ones observed in each MS. These results can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. What type of fuel/energy do you use in your car / in the car you usually drive? (Multiple answers possible)

3.1.3. Fuel prices and fuel knowledge

The participants were asked to rate how concerned they are about fuel prices. At the overall level, it is shown that 32.9% of the sample is overwhelmingly concerned about fuel prices whereas only 7.7% is not really concerned. In this regard, the prices of all the fuel types concerns the majority of EU citizens leading to the necessity of developing a common and transparent method for displaying FPC of both CFs and AFs. The results are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Are you...about fuel prices?

The next section investigated the knowledge with respect to AFs. Firstly, consumers were asked to rate their knowledge level of AFs by choosing one of four different options, those shown in Figure 5. The most well-known AF type is “Electric power and/or Petrol/Diesel” while hydrogen present the least acceptance of the respondents at the overall level. In overall level, 50.0% of the participants stated that they have deeper knowledge about Electric power separate or combined with petrol/diesel. For the rest of the AFs the option "I have heard about it, but I do not have more information" ranked first reaching around 50.0% of the answers collected. This outcome raises the need for providing more information about AFs to the consumers in order to achieve higher rates of engagement.

Figure 5. Please evaluate your knowledge level regarding the fuels listed.

Afterwards, the next question asked the respondents to perceive what fuel type among the AFs would be less expensive for powering a vehicle. They asked to choose among the following fuel types; (1) Hydrogen, (2) Electric power, (3) Combination of electric power and/or petrol/diesel (hybrid), (4) CNG, (5) LPG and (6) Biofuels (highly blended (h.b.)). It derives from the results that the majority of respondents considered the electricity as the cheapest fuel type to power a vehicle with a percentage of 25.4% and then the combination of electricity with petrol/diesel engine (hybrid) with a percentage of 19.1%. The ranking of AFs in overall level is as follows; "LPG" 15.6%, "CNG" 15.4%, "Hydrogen" 15.1% and "Biofuels" 9.5%. This can be correlated with the results of the previous question in which, electricity or electricity coupled with petrol/diesel are by far the most recognizable AF types. The answers received in this question heavily depend on the information available about AFs, their penetration in the fuel market and the initiatives taken by the authorities to publicize them and enhance their use.

3.1.4. Environmental awareness

The environmental awareness question asked how considering the environmental impact of an option would affect the consumption choices of the respondents. In this question, the respondents were asked to choose among four different options. At an overall level, it is shown that the majority (58.6%) is somewhat concerned about the environment and make consumption choices based on their environmental impact. A percentage of 23.5% is very concerned about the environment whereas only 2.8% is not at all concerned about the environment. Therefore, it is evident that EU citizens are concerned of the environmental issues and they take into consideration environmental aspects when they make consumption choices.

3.1.5. Vehicle purchase choices and criteria

The next section concerned the aspects concerning the purchase of a vehicle, in relation to the AFs. The respondents were asked about the reasons, which would affect their willingness to buy their next vehicle. Respondents were offered several options and were able to select more than one option so to indicate all the reasons, which apply to their case. The results showed that consumers considered more than one factor before they select a vehicle. According to results, responders stated that the appearance and comfort of the vehicle is a priority in selecting a new vehicle. In this line, aspects such as driving characteristics, quality of equipment and features, safety and car practicality are considered as well in order to ensure that the new vehicle will be suitable to the buyer's needs. The factors, which show higher rates, are Vehicle Price (24.3%), Fuel Costs (20.0%), Driving range (15.6%) (How far can this vehicle drive with a full tank or full battery) and Environmental performance (12.6%). The remaining options were selected by less than 10.0% of the participants. Results are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Which reason(s) would affect your willingness to buy your next vehicle? (Multiple answers possible)

3.1.6. Information display and distribution for fuel prices

The last section of questions refers the display and distribution of the details for the AFs and their prices. The respondents were introduced to the scope of this PSA with an introduction before they continue the online questionnaire. The first question asked about the preferred frequency of the price updates under €/100km methodology. Regarding the frequency of updating the FPC prices, respondents indicated that the most preferred option would be once in a month with a percentage of 62.3%. A group of 25.0% suggested updating the FPC prices once per three months and the rest of respondents chose to see the FPC prices updated after more than three months.

Then, consumers were asked about their preferences in relation to the display of the FPC prices (€/100km) elsewhere from the filling stations. This question did not provide any options and it had an *open box* allowing the respondents to give their feedback. It is noted that respondents were able to skip this question. The different answers given, as well as the corresponding percentages, can be seen in Figure 7. As it shown, a percentage of 37.3% indicated the display of FPC price (€/100km) on a specialized website or a portal. They also suggested using official websites of the relevant ministries or the oil companies' websites to guarantee the unbiased estimation of fuel prices. The second option (14.4%) was to display the information at car dealerships.

Consumers realized the relation between the fuel price per 100 km and the vehicle consumption, thereof, they would prefer to see this information at auto shops, auto clubs as well as include this information in the vehicle's brochure. The third most proposed option (8.4%) was to publish the information on press, newspapers, and car magazines. It is noted that a minority of respondents was not committed to the objectives of the PSA and they were not sure if they understand or need this information. This result shows the need for further dissemination and effective communication of the common methodology to the consumers.

Figure 7. In the filling stations, where would you prefer to see information about €/100 km displayed? – Other

3.2. Overall results interpretation

This section presents the overall results and outcomes interpretation. The basic data analysis that was carried out in the previous section enabled the under-the-same protocol spectrum and the equal weight theorises for the participating MS. The outcome of the analysis aimed to gather information concerning the current vehicle purchasing criteria, environmental awareness, as well as prepare the ground for the identification of recommendations on the most effective ways to communicate to the European consumers the FPC at the filling stations and through an online tool in a transparent and complete manner. In terms of demographics, the results show a balanced representation of “male” and “female” respondents regarding the age and the urbanisation level while “other” respondents present a small percentage. In parallel, Figure 8 depicts small vehicles to represent the lowest share (11.1% to 15.8%) in both three urbanisation categories. On the other hand, medium vehicles are used by the majority of respondents (58.9% to 62.5%). However, the share of small vehicles is decreased (11.1%) in rural areas in comparison to urban and suburban areas (15.1% and 15.8%) whereas the share of large vehicles is higher in rural areas (25.1%) and is lower in urban and suburban areas (21.8% and

19.8%). Therefore, the impact of age and urbanisation level is low regarding the selection of vehicle size; however, these features provide an indication on respondents' mobility trends in each case.

Figure 8 Vehicle size - Urbanisation Level

This categorisation allowed the analysis of the questionnaire and the identification of the independent parameters that affect respondents' perspective in relation to FPC. In addition, this approach enabled the development of more personalised recommendations aiming to satisfy the requirements – needs of specific consumer groups. The participants were asked to evaluate their knowledge level regarding AFs. The results show the electric-powered vehicles and hybrid electric vehicles to be the most well-known, whereas hydrogen vehicles are the least known AFVs. Almost half of the respondents are interested in learning more about the AFs while it was explicitly stated that 'Further education on this topic is needed'. Respondents showed interest in getting informed not only about the fuel costs of the different fuel types but also expressed the “need for really honest and good information about the environmental impact of the various fuels, the costs of car and fuel, etc.”

Furthermore, the average distance respondents cover daily is presented in Figure 9. Respondents who cover distances less than 20km are more interested in selecting a cost-effective vehicle (25.6%) compared with respondents covering longer distances (23.7% & 22.5%). They also have the greater share regarding the environmental performance of the vehicle (13.2%). When covering an average distance, factors, which present a peak, are the fuel costs (20.6%) and the fuel station availability (10.2%). Respondents who drive more than 50km a day are interested in the driving range of the vehicle (17.2%) and they present a decreased share on the environmental performance of the vehicle (12.0%).

Figure 9. Purchase decision factors-Common distance

Considering the question concerning the criteria of purchasing a vehicle, the overall results show that the two most significant factors are the price of the vehicle with a percentage of 24% and the cost of the fuels with a percentage of 20%. Hence, the FPC is proved essential for facilitating the consumers to compare fuel prices under the same unit. Because of FPC prices (€/100km), a significant percentage of respondents ask for more details about the values used for these estimations”.

Considering the purposes of the PSA, respondents seek for a holistic study which will consider the current engine technologies in relation to the emissions and consumption and it will provide valuable guidelines, taking into account both environmental considerations and drivers’ preferences. In terms of location of the information to be displayed at a filling station, respondents indicated that they would prefer to be able to compare fuel prices while they refuel/recharge their vehicle. Besides filling stations, they would prefer to find information regarding the fuel/energy price comparison, in €/100 km, on the internet, different media (i.e., TV, Radio, etc.) or car dealerships. As for the format of the information, it was concluded to be tested in pilots, displaying a table format with the FPC prices of the fuel types, accompanied by contact information in case they needed support with the displayed information.

Finally, in the last question, respondents were kindly asked to add their feedback/comments in relation to the online questionnaire and the purposes of the PSA. An aspect to be measured is that respondents identified negative aspects of AFVs including the price of purchasing an AFV and the limited availability of filling/charging points. Respondents also shared their opinion in relation to electric vehicles specifically. In fact, they believed that the purchase prices of a pure electric vehicle (PEV) might be not affordable by all the consumers, as settled before. On the contrary, respondents worried about the quality and the price of the CFs. A share of respondents appeared to have a more consolidate opinion in relation to AFVs. They expressed interesting arguments about mostly hydrogen and diesel vehicles pointing out pros and cons of both vehicle categories. All these aspects were taken into consideration from the PSA consortium in order to develop a

common methodology for FPC as well as raise awareness in relation to the environmental impact of CF powered vehicles and enhance the penetration of AFs in mobility market.

3.3. FPC common methodology

The results from the online questionnaire paved the way for a transparent, consistent, and consumer-oriented methodology for estimating the FPC and communicating it effectively to the public. This section is dedicated to the outline of the FPC common methodology, which was developed and evaluated at pilot actions. [15]

The principal formula for the price calculations in €/100km, which is described in the Implementing Regulation (EU) 2018/732 and is tested during this PSA, is the following:

$$FPC\ price\left(\frac{\text{€}}{100km}\right) = Vehicle\ Consumption\left(\frac{\text{fuel unit}}{100km}\right) \cdot Average\ Fuel\ Price\left(\frac{\text{€}}{\text{fuel unit}}\right)$$

The *first factor* refers to the reference WLTP consumption for the compared fuel types and the *second factor* refers to the average price of the compared fuel types.

3.3.1. Vehicle WLTP consumption

The first step is the selection of the vehicles obtained from at least one segment (and maximum of three segments). To keep as close as possible to the mind-set of consumers, the bestselling segment is selected yearly (calendar). In that segment, at least a top three of bestselling vehicles are identified per fuel type. This is done on type level (including all models). This step is performed for all the fuel types available in the MS. This can vary per vehicle segment. In case a certain fuel type (commonly hydrogen) is not available at all, then this fuel type is left out of the calculation.

The reference vehicle consumption is calculated as the sales-weighted average World Harmonized Light-Duty Vehicles Test Procedure (WLTP) combined consumption of at least a top three of best-selling vehicle types, considering the previous calendar year. This calculation is performed for at least one segment for the 6 fuels if available. Per selected vehicle type, a sales-weighted average WLTP consumption of the available fuel versions is calculated. Based on these averages the sales-weighted average WLTP is calculated per fuel per segment. In certain cases (such as hydrogen vehicles) due to the lack of models, this sample can be smaller than three models. Thus, the vehicle consumption calculated is the sales-weighted average of at least the top 3 best-selling cars in one segment based on the average per selected vehicle type in that segment.

To increase the accuracy of estimations and to ensure the comparability of data, the vehicle categories, which are considered, are the Mono-fuel vehicles (liquid, gas), the Pure Electric Vehicles (PEVs), and the Fuel cell vehicles (FCV). In the case of limited data of mono-fuel gas vehicles, bi-fuel gas vehicles may be used for calculating the reference consumption, if the relevant WLTP data is available. Hence, flex-fuel vehicles, hybrid electric vehicles and converted vehicles are not considered for the FPC calculations.

3.3.2. Average fuel price

The calculation of FPC prices requires an estimation of the average prices of the diverse fuel types measured in euros/national currency per CF type unit for the previous calendar quarter. Accordingly, the FPC is updated quarterly (March, June, September, and December) based on these updated prices. Recommended data sources include (1) official national fuel observatories, (2) automotive fuel retailers, (3) National Access Points (NAPs), and (4) national statistic agencies. The data from these sources allows the estimation of the average prices of both CFs and AFs. As CFs are considered the petrol and the diesel, while AFs are determined by the Art. 2 of the AFID to be electricity, hydrogen, biofuels, as defined in point (i) of Article 2 of Directive 2009/28/EC, synthetic and paraffinic fuels, CNG and LPG. The highly blend biofuels, as well as synthetic and paraffinic fuels, are not included in the FPC due to the lack of data availability.

Special attention should be paid at the units of the fuel prices in correspondence with fuel consumption units. For instance, the official fuel consumption figures for NG/biomethane are in m³/100km instead of kg/100km, which was the case in NEDC. In parallel, the CNG price at filling stations is currently in €/kg. To enable calculations in the same units, the CNG values will have to be multiplied by 0.717 (the density of methane).

The average electricity price is preferred to be calculated as one single price (based on the relevant charging mix). Furthermore, for those MS that cannot provide one single price, it is recommended to display two average prices, one for public charging and one for home charging. In this regard, if public charging is not available, the average price of the home charging only will be displayed. These alternatives are recommended in order to facilitate MS with limited data for electricity charging to include the electricity in the FPC.

3.3.3. Application in EU countries

The fuel price comparison was introduced as mandatory for all MS from December 7, 2020 at filling stations, which are selected in MS level aligned with the publication “Recommendation from the PSA on fuel price comparison: assisting Member States with the implementation of Article 7.3 of Directive 2014/94/EU (Fuel Price Comparison)” by the Publications Office of European Commission. The cases of Germany and the Netherlands are presented indicatively to demonstrate the implementation of the FPC framework and the Article 7 (3) of Directive 2014/94/ EU.

In Germany, on June 25, 2021, as part of the amendment to the Energy Industry Act (EnWG) and the amendment to the Energy Consumption Labelling Act (EnVKG), the German Bundestag decided to introduce energy cost comparisons at filling stations for the first time. The introduction of the energy cost comparison serves to implement Article 7 (3) of Directive 2014/94/ EU on the development of infrastructure for alternative fuels. According to this, filling stations with more than six multi-product pumps are obliged to compare the costs of various energy sources (including petrol, diesel, electricity, natural gas, hydrogen) in € per 100 km visible for selected vehicle segments at petrol pumps or in the sales room. The costs of the diverse fuel and energy source market are thus presented to consumers in a way that makes them comparable, thereby sensitizing them to alternative drive systems and energy sources for passenger cars. (<https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/DE/Artikel/Energie/2021-08-pkw-energiekostenvergleich.html>). Respectively, in the Netherlands, from December 2020, the average fuel prices per 100 km will be displayed at manned petrol stations along the highway. The prices of six fuels are shown: petrol, diesel, LPG, electricity, hydrogen, and CNG based on consumption per 100 km. The prices are calculated based on the consumption of the three most sold new cars within a car segment in the past calendar year. (weighted averages) The selected German and Dutch FPC displays are presented in Figure 10(<https://www.rvo.nl/onderwerpen/brandstofprijvergelijking>).

Figure 10 German (left) and Dutch (right) FPC display

4. Conclusions

Reducing the environmental impact of the transport sector is a viable strategy towards sustainability. Transport is responsible for harmful GHG emissions, noise, and climate change. It accounts for the 24% of global CO₂ emissions (if we only consider CO₂ emissions from energy), therefore; investing in efficient and clean transport infrastructure and services (passenger and freight) is fundamental to achieving sustainable economic growth. For the above reasons, the AFID introduced a consumer-oriented framework towards AFs, which aims to promote AFs to the consumers, increase consumers' environmental awareness and provide fuel price transparency as well as display FPC information without confusing the consumers. In this regard, the FPC4Consumers PSA was implemented, aiming to support the consistent implementation of the provisions of Art. 7.3 of the AFID, and define the format, content, and location of the information to be displayed at the filling stations.

Within the PSA's framework, an online survey was conducted targeting on understanding of consumers' perspectives on FPC. Accordingly, this study presents the in-depth analysis and evaluation of the online questionnaire results. This online survey aimed to provide insights regarding the contents, format, and location of the information on fuel prices to be compared and displayed at filling/charging stations by taking into account the perspective of the consumers among EU. The questions asked, offered an insight on how consumers perceive AFs in relation to their costs and environmental impact as well as on their willingness to select a new AFV in their next purchase. In addition, the results allow a better understanding of not only consumers' needs but also their arguments relating to AFs. The survey collected a sample of 7612 respondents among EU, covering different ages, dwelling environments and vehicles' preferences and needs. It is worth mentioning that suggestions and recommendations provided by respondents were utilised enabling consumer-oriented and proper implementation of the provisions of the Article 7.3. Therefore, the outcome of the analysis resulted in the identification of recommendations on the most effective ways to communicate to the European consumers the FPC at the fuel station in a transparent and complete manner.

Over and above that, all these aspects were taken into consideration as to develop a common methodology for FPC as well as raise awareness in relation to the environmental impact of CF powered vehicles and enhance the penetration of AFs in mobility market. The benefits of the common methodology can be summarized on the fact that there are no assumptions and it is based on the WLTP consumption, which is a common and accessible parameter among all vehicles. Thereby, from this perspective, all vehicles available in the EU mobility market can be incorporated. To conclude, the results from the online questionnaire paved the way for a transparent, consistent, and consumer-oriented methodology for estimating the FPC and communicating it effectively to the public.

Acknowledgments

This research received funding from the European Union "Connecting Europe Facility" Programme Support Action on "Assisting Member States with the implementation of Article 7.3 of Directive 2014/94/EU (Fuel Price Comparison)", under the reference no.: MOVE/B4/GRANT/CEF/PSA/2018-491.

The results of the survey (online questionnaire) were reported in the public Deliverable D6.3 "Final Report" which was submitted in the framework of the "Connecting Europe Facility" Programme Support Action on "Assisting Member States with the implementation of Article 7.3 of Directive 2014/94/EU (Fuel Price Comparison)". (<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2832/189449>)

The FPC common methodology is in accordance with the publication "Recommendation from the PSA on fuel price comparison: assisting Member States with the implementation of Article 7.3 of Directive 2014/94/EU (fuel price comparison)" by the Publications Office of European Commission (<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2832/89250>)

References

1. EUROPE F. TRANSPORT ENERGY & RENEWABLES IN THE EU – WHAT THE LATEST COMMISSION DATA TELLS US: FARM EUROPE; 2021, January [updated 29/01/2021 cited 2022

- 10/02/2022]. Available from: <https://www.farm-europe.eu/blog-en/transport-energy-renewables-in-the-eu-what-the-latest-commission-data-tells-us/>
2. EUROSTAT. Renewable energy used in transport increasing: eurostat; 2020 [cited 2022 18/02/2022]. Available from: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/energy/data/shares>
 3. CAIT. Climate Data Explorer: CAIT Climate Data Explorer; 2016 [cited 2022 10/01/2022]. Available from: https://www.climatewatchdata.org/data-explorer/historical-emissions?historical-emissions-data-sources=cait&historical-emissions-gases=co2&historical-emissions-regions=All%20Selected&historical-emissions-sectors=total-including-lucf%2Ctransportation&page=1&sort_col=country&sort_dir=ASC
 4. DIRECTIVE 2014/94/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 22 October 2014 on the deployment of alternative fuels infrastructure (2014).
 5. Bacovsky D. The role of renewable transport fuels in decarbonizing road transport-deployment barriers and policy recommendations. IEA. 2021;58(IEA technology collaboration programmes advanced motor fuels annex).
 6. Ghadikolaei MA, Wong PK, Cheung CS, et al. Why is the world not yet ready to use alternative fuel vehicles? *Heliyon*. 2021 2021/07/01/;7(7):e07527. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07527>.
 7. Commission E, Mobility D-Gf, Transport. Consumer survey and test on fuel price comparison methodology : final report. Publications Office; 2018.
 8. BLOOMFIELD R, NELSON MW, SOLTES E. Gathering Data for Archival, Field, Survey, and Experimental Accounting Research. *Journal of Accounting Research*. 2016;54(2):341-395. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-679X.12104>.
 9. Glasow PA. Fundamentals of survey research methodology. 2005 April 2005;18(MITRE Washington C3 Centre):27.
 10. Schleyer TK, Forrest JL. Methods for the design and administration of web-based surveys. *J Am Med Inform Assoc*. 2000 Jul-Aug;7(4):416-425. doi: 10.1136/jamia.2000.0070416. PubMed PMID: 10887169; eng.
 11. Mullock JL-PP. The 1998 Data Protection Act. 2000. English.
 12. Sheikh AA. The Data Protection (Amendment) Act, 2003: the Data Protection Directive and its implications for medical research in Ireland. *European journal of health law*. 2005 Dec;12(4):357-72. doi: 10.1163/157180905775088568. PubMed PMID: 16454366; eng.
 13. EUROSTAST. Degree of urbanisation (DEGURBA): eurostat; 2018 [cited 2019]. Available from: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/degree-of-urbanisation/background>
 14. REGULATION (EEC) No 4064/89 MERGER PROCEDURE. Article 6(1)(b) NON-OPPOSITION (Case COMP/M.1406 — Hyundai/Kia), (1999).
 15. Commission E, Mobility D-Gf, Transport, et al. Recommendation from the PSA on fuel price comparison : assisting Member States with the implementation of Article 7.3 of Directive 2014/94/EU (fuel price comparison). Publications Office; 2021.